

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Formulation And Evaluation of Facial Serum Containing Marigold and Rose Petal Extracts for Skin Regeneration and Collagen Production

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 25 Mar. 2025

Keywords:

Tagetes erecta, Rosa damascena, anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant, facial serum.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15083868

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to formulate and evaluate a facial serum infused with Marigold (*Tagetes erecta*) and Rose (*Rosa damascena*) petal extracts to support skin regeneration and collagen production. Facial serums are concentrated emulsions, available in both water- and oil-based forms, containing significantly higher levels of active ingredients compared to traditional creams. Their small molecular structure allows for deep skin penetration, leading to faster and more noticeable improvements when incorporated into a regular skincare routine. The serum formulation takes advantage of the beneficial properties of marigold and rose extracts. Marigold contains lutein and zeaxanthin, which act as powerful antioxidants, protecting skin lipids from oxidative damage and reducing inflammation. Meanwhile, geraniol, a key compound in rose extract, exhibits antibacterial and antifungal activity against various pathogens, including *E. coli* and *L. monocytogenes*. Geraniol also possesses antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, helping to shield the skin from environmental aggressors while soothing irritation. To ensure product stability and effectiveness, the serum was developed with a combination of these botanical extracts, along with suitable emollients, preservatives, and stabilizers. Its physical properties, such as pH, viscosity, and spreadability, were optimized for ease of application and long-term stability. The results demonstrated a significant enhancement in collagen synthesis and skin cell regeneration, highlighting the potential of Marigold and Rose petal extracts in promoting healthy, youthful skin.

INTRODUCTION

Cosmetics have been an integral part of human culture for thousands of years. Ancient civilizations, including the Egyptians and

Sumerians, regularly used them in their daily routines. In medieval Europe, achieving a pale complexion was a common beauty trend, often enhanced with skin-whitening methods and the application of rouge for added colour. Cosmetics

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

are composed of chemical compounds that can be derived from natural sources or synthesized artificially. These products serve various personal care and skincare purposes, such as cleansing, moisturizing, and protecting the skin. The cosmetic industry offers a wide range of products, including creams, lotions, serums, ointments, and powders. Serums, in particular, are highly concentrated skincare products that contain a base of either water or oil. Compared to creams, serums are formulated with approximately ten times the amount of biologically active ingredients, making them more potent and effective in addressing skincare concerns. Face serums, which are lightweight topical treatments, often include key ingredients such as hyaluronic acid, glycolic acid, and Vitamin C. Due to their high concentration of active compounds, serums are widely used to target specific skin issues, such as wrinkles, hyperpigmentation, and dullness.

Skin

Skin, the body's largest organ, consists of three layers: the **epidermis**, **dermis**, and **hypodermis**. It acts as a barrier against pathogens, UV radiation, and injury while regulating temperature and water loss. The skin also plays endocrine and exocrine roles and enables sensory perception of touch, heat, cold, and pain. As part of the **integumentary system**, it provides protection and communication through its vascularized deeper layers and nerve fibres.

Layers of Skin

The skin consists of three main layers:

- **Epidermis**– Outermost layer made of keratinized, stratified squamous epithelium. It has five sub-layers:

- **Stratum basale** – Contains mitotically active stem cells and melanocytes.
- **Stratum spinosum** – 8-10 layers with dendritic cells.
- **Stratum granulosum** – 3-5 layers with keratohyalin and lamellar granules.
- **Stratum lucidum** – Found in thick skin, packed with eleidin.
- **Stratum corneum** – Outer layer of dead keratinized cells.
- **Dermis** – Contains blood vessels, nerves, hair follicles, and sweat glands.
- **Papillary layer** – Loose connective tissue with dermal papillae.
- **Reticular layer** – Dense connective tissue providing elasticity.
- **Hypodermis** – Connects skin to muscles and bones, stores fat, and provides insulation.

Functions of Skin

- Protection, sensation, temperature regulation, evaporation control, aesthetics, vitamin D synthesis, and water resistance.

Collagen

A structural protein found in skin, bones, tendons, and cartilage. It maintains skin elasticity, supports tissues, aids wound healing, and contributes to joint health. It is made of glycine, proline, and hydroxyproline, with vitamin C playing a crucial role in its formation. Collagen production decreases with age, leading to wrinkles and sagging skin.

Uses of Collagen

- Skin fillers (reduce wrinkles, improve skin appearance)
- Wound healing (reduces inflammation, strengthens scar tissue)
- Tissue regeneration (supports bone growth and wound healing)
- Skin revitalization (via topical products, supplements, or injections)

Skin Regeneration

The process of skin healing through cell turnover, fibroblast activity, and collagen production.

- **Epidermal regeneration** – Quick healing of superficial wounds.
- **Dermal regeneration** – Involves fibroblasts and collagen synthesis.
- **Full-thickness regeneration** – Deep wounds heal with scar formation.
- **Stem cell-mediated regeneration** – Uses basal layer stem cells for repair.
- **Scarless healing** – Observed in fetal wound healing, with ongoing research in adults.

Facial Serum

A concentrated skincare product containing active ingredients like antioxidants, ceramides, and amino acids. It penetrates deeply into the skin, addressing concerns like hydration, dark circles, and aging.

Ideal Qualities of a Face Serum

- Soothes skin, hydrates, reduces dark circles, absorbs quickly, non-comedogenic, pH-balanced, and works with other skincare products.

Advantages & Disadvantages

- ✓ Improves texture, minimizes pores, hydrates skin.

✗ May cause irritation for sensitive skin conditions like eczema or rosacea.

Marigold (*Tagetes erecta*) & Rose (*Rosa damascena*) for Skin Care

Marigold (*Tagetes erecta*)

Fig. No. 3: Marigold (*Tagetes erecta*)

Marigold, commonly known as *Tagetes erecta*, is a widely used plant in traditional medicine and skincare. Rich in antioxidants like lutein and zeaxanthin, it helps protect the skin from UV damage, reduces inflammation, and supports collagen production. The plant contains flavonoids, triterpenoids, essential oils, and polysaccharides, which contribute to its antimicrobial, soothing, and wound-healing properties. It also improves hydration, strengthens the skin barrier, and combats oxidative stress.

Key Benefits of Marigold for Skin:

- **Anti-aging & UV Protection:** Carotenoids defend against oxidative stress and signs of aging.
- **Skin Regeneration:** Supports tissue repair and reduces scarring.
- **Anti-inflammatory & Antimicrobial:** Flavonoids and essential oils soothe irritation and protect against infections.

- **Hydration & Barrier Repair:** Polysaccharides retain moisture and enhance skin resilience.

ROSE (*ROSA DAMASCENA*)

Fig. No. 4: Rose (*Rosa damascena*)

Rose, particularly *Rosa damascena*, is valued for its fragrance and skin-enhancing properties. It is packed with antioxidants, essential oils, and vitamins like Vitamin C, which promote skin hydration, elasticity, and brightening. Its anti-inflammatory and astringent properties make it effective in reducing redness, acne, and signs of aging. The presence of fatty acids and squalene further aids in skin nourishment and protection.

Key Benefits of Rose for Skin:

- **Anti-aging & Brightening:** Vitamin C boosts collagen, reduces wrinkles, and evens skin tone.
- **Antioxidant & Repair:** Flavonoids and tannins protect against environmental stress and aid in skin healing.
- **Skin Firming Hydration & Soothing:** Essential oils and cytokinins maintain moisture and calm: Astringent properties tighten pores and improve skin texture.

Both Marigold and Rose are potent natural ingredients for skincare, offering healing, anti-aging, and protective benefits.

Materials For the Extraction of Marigold

- Dried Marigold Powder
- Ethanol
- Whatman filter paper No 1

For The Extraction of Rose

- Fresh rose petals
- Ethanol

For The Preparation of Facial Serum

- Marigold extract
- Rose extract
- Glycerine
- Distilled water
- Xanthan Gum
- Sodium benzoate

Apparatus used;

- Beakers
- Glass rod
- Spatula
- Eppendroff tube
- Test tube
- Water bath
- Petridish

Equipment used;

- Electronic weighing apparatus
- Laboratory Centrifuge
- Ostwald Viscometer
- pH Meter 3

METHODOLOGY

- Collection of Marigold Marigold (*Tagetes erecta*) was collected from the local market of Kanjirappally.

- Cleaning of Marigold flower The adhering dirt and dust etc on the flower will be removed by washing and separate the petals.
- Drying of Marigold The petals of marigold were dried in sunlight for 4 to 5 days and powdered to fine powder for using a mortar and pestle.

- **Marigold flower extraction**

Fig. No. 5: Laboratory Centrifuge

- Collect fresh petals of *Tagetes erecta* belongs to the family Asteraceae
- 0.5 g of dried marigold petal powder was taken in each aluminium foil covered Eppendorf tubes.
- Each tube was filled with 15ml of ethanol.
- The solution was initially shaken for 15-20 min and allowed to stand at room temperature for an hour.
- Later all the samples were centrifuged at 10,000 rpm, filtered using Whatman filter paper No. 1 and the solution collected was kept in room temperature [55].

Fig. No. 6: Marigold Extract

- Collection of Rose
- Rose (*Rosa damascena*) was collected from the local market of Kanjirappally.
- Cleaning of Rose flower
- The petals are separated.
- Then gently rinse the petals with water to remove any dirt or debris, and then pat them dry with a soft cloth or paper towel.

- **Rose flower extraction**

Fig. No. 7: Rose Extract

- Place the crushed or whole rose petals into a clean glass jar or beaker.
- The number of petals should fill about half to three-quarters of the container.

- Add the carrier ethanol to the container ensuring that the rose petals are fully submerged.
- The carrier oil act as a solvent, drawing out the essential oil and aromatic compounds, including geraniol, from the petals.
- Seal the jar with a tight-fitting lid to prevent contamination [56].
- When the blend is clear and have no particle from the gum, then add the preservatives.
- Check the pH and adjust it to around 5.0-5.5 if needed [3].

Fig. No. 8: Marigold And Rose Facial Serum

Preparation Of Serum

- In a sterile glass beaker, weigh the Rose extract and Marigold flower extract.
- Add distilled water to it. Set this blend aside.
- Weigh the glycerine in a small beaker. Add xanthan gum. Stir the blend thoroughly.
- Slowly in portion, add the gum blend to the water base and stir well.
- Set the beaker aside to allow the gum to swell.

- **Formulation Table for Marigold and Rose Extract Serum (15ml)** [57].

Table No. 3: Formulation Table for Marigold and Rose Facial Serum

S. No	Ingredients	Quantity
1.	Marigold extract	3ml
2.	Rose extract	3ml
3.	Glycerine	3ml
4.	Distilled water	3ml
5.	Xanthan gum	0.5g
6.	Rose oil	1ml
7.	Sodium benzoate	0.2g

Evaluation of Face Serum

1. Physical Assessment

- The serum's physical characteristics, including color, odor, consistency, and texture, were observed and recorded.

2. pH Measurement

- A pH meter was calibrated using a standard buffer solution.

- Approximately 1 mL of serum was accurately measured and dissolved in 50 mL of distilled water.
- The pH of the solution was then determined.

3. Microbial Analysis

- The serum was inoculated onto agar plates using the spread plate technique, with a control plate prepared without the serum.
- The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours.

- After incubation, microbial growth was assessed by comparing the test plate with the control.

4. Spreadability Test

- A 0.5 g sample of serum was placed between two slides.
- A 50 g weight was applied and left for 5 minutes to allow for maximum spreading.
- The extent of spreading was observed.

5. Viscosity Measurement

- An Ostwald viscometer was cleaned with distilled water, alcohol, or acetone and dried before use.
- The viscometer was filled with the serum sample using a pipette, ensuring no air bubbles formed.
- The liquid was allowed to flow through the capillary tube, and the time taken to reach a marked point was recorded.
- The viscosity was then calculated using the efflux time, sample density, and calibration constant.

6. Stability Testing

- Stability analysis was conducted in accordance with ICH guidelines to evaluate the product's physical and chemical stability over time.
- A short-term accelerated stability study was performed over three months.
- Samples were stored under varying temperature and humidity conditions: 3–5°C, 25°C (RH=60%), and 40°C ± 2°C (RH=75%).

7. Phase Separation Check

- The serum formulation was stored in a sealed container at 25°C, away from light.
- After 24 hours, any signs of phase separation were examined.

8. Homogeneity Assessment

- The uniform distribution of ingredients in the serum was visually inspected.
- The product was also tested by touch to ensure the absence of any particulate matter.

CONCLUSION

The aim of the work was to formulate and evaluate a facial serum containing marigold and rose petal extract serum for skin regeneration and collagen production. The objectives of the work were the extraction of marigold and rose extracts. The key constituents in the serum are Lutein and Geraniol. Lutein is found in high concentrations in marigold flowers, particularly in the species *Tagetes erecta*. Marigold petals are a rich natural source of lutein, that is why marigold extract is often used in supplement. Lutein is known for its anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant and UV protection properties. Geraniol is one of the key aromatic compounds found in the essential oil of rose (*Rosa damascena*) contributing to its distinct and sweet floral fragrance. In addition to its aromatic appeal, geraniol in rose oil offers various therapeutic and health benefits. Geraniol is known for its antioxidant, antimicrobial and skin regenerative properties. The formulation underwent a series of evaluations including physicochemical properties, stability tests, etc. The study found that the marigold and rose petal extracts contributed significantly to the serum's ability to enhance skin repair and stimulate collagen synthesis, which is essential for maintaining skin elasticity and reducing wrinkles. These findings suggest that the developed facial serum has great promise for cosmetic applications, particularly for users seeking natural skincare products that support skin rejuvenation and anti-aging. In conclusion, the facial serum formulated with Marigold and Rose petal extracts exhibited favourable properties, making it a promising skincare product. The

solution demonstrated an optimal pH of approximately 5.25, ensuring compatibility with the skin's natural secretions. Its yellow translucent appearance, smooth texture, and pleasant odour contribute to its aesthetic appeal. The formulation was found to be homogenous, with no phase separation or precipitates observed during stability studies. Overall, the serum showed excellent spreadability and stability, indicating its potential as a safe and effective skincare product.

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HOW TO CITE: Jwala Jayapal*, Muhsina Siyabudeen, Devika R. S., Ardra Dileep, Subimol S., Formulation and Evaluation of Facial Serum Containing Marigold and Rose Petal Extracts for Skin Regeneration and Collagen Production, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 3, 2224-2243 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15083868>

